

Synthesis of Cerium and Gallium Doped Mesoporous Bioactive Glass Nanoparticles

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ABSTRACT

According to the IUPAC definition, porous materials are divided into three classes: microporous (pore size < 2 nm), mesoporous (2–50 nm) and macroporous (>50 nm) [1]. Ordered mesoporous silica was first discovered in 1992 [2], and proposed as a drug delivery system in 2001 [3]. Since then silica-based glass microspheres, such as MCM-41, SBA-15 or MCM-48 representing ordered mesoporous inorganic materials, have been considered as ideal materials for incorporation of drugs, genes and other therapeutic agents acting as carrier and control release systems. In this study, the synthesis of mesoporous bioactive glass nanoparticles, consisting of a silicate network modified by Ca and Ce or Ga ions, has been studied for possible applications in cancer treatment or incorporation into nanocomposite scaffolds for bone regeneration.

Tetraethylorthosilicate (TEOS, 100%, VWR International), hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB, BioXtra, ≥99%, Sigma-Aldrich), ethyl acetate (99.7%, Centralchem), ammonium hydroxide (ACS reagent, 28.0 - 30.0% NH₃ basis, Sigma-Aldrich), Cerium nitrate hexahydrate (99.95%, Treibacher) and gallium nitrate hexahydrate (99.999%, Alchemica) were used as starting materials for synthesis of mesoporous bioactive glass nanoparticles (MBGNPs).

Cerium doped mesoporous bioactive glass nanoparticles (MBGNPs) in the 60SiO₂-(40-x)CaO-xCe₂O₃ system and gallium doped MBGNPs in the 60SiO₂-(40-x)CaO-xGa₂O₃ system, where x stands for 0, 1, 3 and 5 mole %, were obtained by micro-emulsion assisted sol-gel method. First, 2.8 g of CTAB templating agent was dissolved in 150 mL deionized water, and 40 ml of ethyl acetate was added. Ammonium hydroxide (3.66 ml) was then added and mixed at room temperature. TEOS (14.4 ml) and appropriate quantities of calcium nitrate tetrahydrate, cerium nitrate hexahydrate or gallium nitrate hexahydrate were added step wise to the solution within a 30 minutes time interval, and the solution was left for 4 hours. Afterwards the precipitates were filtered and washed with deionized water and EtOH to remove unreacted precursors and remaining salts, and dried at 60°C overnight. Finally, the dried samples were thermally treated at 650 °C/3 h (heating rate 1 °C min⁻¹) to remove the surfactant and nitrate groups and to stabilize the glassy phase.

Micro-emulsion assisted sol-gel method allowed the preparation of MBGNPs with spherical shape, monomodal size distribution with the mean equivalent diameter of 150 nm and a low degree of agglomeration. SEM micrographs and EDS spectra of undoped MBGNPs are shown in Fig. 1. The results of acid digestion method confirm that the glass nanoparticles contain 12.6 mol % CaO. The high resolution SEM micrographs revealed fine surface structure of the nanoparticles indicating their mesoporous structure.

Figure 1 SEM images of a) undoped, b) doped with 1 mol% cerium and c) doped with 1 mol% gallium Mesoporous Bioactive Glasses produced by Micro-Emulsion Sol-Gel method.

Synthesis of nanoparticles with up to 1 mol% of Ce and Ga yielded nanoparticles of size, shape, and surface pore structure similar to those of the undoped MBGNPs. Increasing the content of dopants up to 3 and 5 mol % resulted in deformation of the spherical shape of the nanoparticles and yielded elongated pineal shaped particles with aspect ratio 5:3. In addition, calcium content decreased significantly (down to 4.4 mol% CaO for gallium and 0.7 mol CaO for cerium), most likely due to replacement of Ca in the glass structure with the ions of the dopants. The influence of doping on specific surface and mesoporosity of synthesized nanoparticles has been evaluated and critically discussed. Specific surface area increased with 1 mol% of doping, 345 m²/g to 412 m²/g for Ce and 486 m²/g for Ga. Increasing the content of dopants up to 3 and 5 mol% resulted in decreasing surface area and increasing the size of the mesoporous.

The micro-emulsion assisted sol-gel method yielded monodispersed mesoporous bioactive glass nanoparticles in the system CaO-SiO₂ doped with up to 5 mol % of Ce and Ga, and with low or no agglomeration. Incorporation of higher concentrations of dopants resulted in distortion of the MBGNPs spherical shape and marked decrease of Ca content. The influence of doping specific surface and mesoporosity of synthesized nanoparticles has been studied.

Keywords: Bioactive glass, Cerium, Gallium, Micro-emulsion, Nanoparticles

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